

ISic3005

Latin architrave inscription

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

volcanic

Object

architrave

Editor

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Autopsy

No

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Excavated in the orchestra of the Roman theatre in 1950 by L. de Gregorio (assistente della Soprintendenza alla Antichita di Catania), under the direction of G. Libertini; seen in the theatre no later than 1961 by Manganaro.

Coordinates

37.502709, 15.083659

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory unknown

Physical Description

A rectangular block of black volcanic stone, lightly damaged along the lower edge and at the right end, and rough below and behind (slight damage above the N to the top edge also). There are two cuttings or depressions in the upper surface.

Dimensions

Height 24 cm

Width 98 cm

Depth 48 cm

Layout

A single line of tall letters on the upper part of the front face, with blank space below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: 120 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. T(itō) · Flavio Ionio[---]

Apparatus

Text from photo

Translation (en)

To Titus Flavius Ionus

Commentary

The stone was published by Manganaro in 1961, who suggested that it commemorated the same individual as ISic0352 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0352>], a funerary altar for Titus Fla[vius] Ion[ius]. This link has been accepted by subsequent scholars. However, there has been considerable confusion and uncertainty regarding this stone in other regards. Manganaro described the piece as being made of 'pietra lavica', and suggested that it was an honorific statue base. According to Manganaro the piece was still in the theatre when he published it in 1961. Subsequent scholars (Wilson, Pensabene) have reported a limestone piece which is in the stores of the Museo Civico di Catania (noted as unpublished), and have consistently distinguished the two pieces (beginning with Wilson 1988: 127 n.128; followed by Wilson 1990: 69 and 365 n.118; Wilson 1996: 161 n.35; Pensabene 1996-1997: 71 n.181). Korhonen repeats this report, while also noting the existence of a 'copia in gesso' (2004: 174 n.86) in the Museo Civico. Both a resin cast/squeeze of the face of the inscription, and a plaster cast copy presumably made using this cast/squeeze are preserved in the Museo Civico (both seen in storage in 2017). The plaster cast (heavily discoloured, and giving the appearance of weathered limestone), originally on display in the 1970s at height on the walls of the Museo Civico, is undoubtedly the source of the original belief that there was a second 'limestone' version of the original inscription, and it is safe to conclude that there is in fact only a single such text, in volcanic stone, and probably still in the area of the Roman theatre.

NB The photograph displayed here is of the plaster cast, not of the original.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645354

Bibliography

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Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Civico di Catania